

Managing Editor's Column

Vol. 2, No. 4; April 28, 1996

Dear Readers:

The current issue of J.UCS (Vol. 2, No.4) contains three high quality theoretical papers. I do hope you will enjoy reading them!

The next two issues will be special issues edited by C. Calude (University of Auckland, New Zealand) and B. Krämer (University of Hagen, Germany), respectively. Both will be substantial contributions to their fields: the first on Algorithmic Information Theory, the second on Distance Teaching!

Further special issues are in preparation! However, J.UCS, as electronic journal has room for as many good quality papers as come in, so keep on sending contributions to J.UCS for possible inclusion.

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
email: hmaurer@iicm.edu

PS: IMPORTANT! Note that J.UCS papers can include arbitrary multimedia material by pointing to arbitrary WWW presentations. This can be done as I am doing right here by linking to my private home page [see <http://www.iicm.tugraz.ac.at/maurer>]: if you click at the URL you come to my home page and find, among other things, some photos of non-scientific activities. You can also include such material as a link (URL) in the list of references. Note that in the printed version the URL will appear as such, but in the Internet version the URL is also clickable!